

INTRODUCTION

Managerial training in digital transformation is relevant due to the rapid development of technologies such as artificial intelligence, automation and big data, which requires managers not only to understand these but to be able to integrate them into business processes.

With digitalization, companies face the need to adapt to new conditions, which requires managers to be able to react quickly to changes. Training highly qualified professionals who can effectively manage under uncertainty is becoming critical to the competitiveness of organizations.

The digital economy requires managers to adopt new approaches to management, including the use of analytics for decision-making, managing remote teams and implementing innovative business models. This creates a need to train a workforce that is able to cope with the new challenges.

Modern managers must have knowledge not only in management but also in related disciplines such as information technology, economics and sociology. This requires revising educational programs and creating interdisciplinary courses.

Thus, the relevance of management training in the digital economy is the need for specialists capable of effective management in the context of rapid changes in technology and market requirements.

The paper aims to analyze the specifics of training managerial personnel in conflict resolution in terms of digital transformation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To study the problem of management training in the digital economy, the authors of this research focused on articles from periodical journals published in the last five years (International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research; Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation; Current Psychology; International Journal of Management, Entrepreneurship, Social Science and Humanities; Scientific Reports; Industrial and Commercial Training; International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management; Revista Inclusiones).

LITERATURE REVIEW

N. A. Shibaeva et al. propose algorithms of innovation policy of forming, training and developing managerial personnel. The authors emphasize the system analysis on applying personnel management potential for solving municipal and regional problems [1].

I. Kryukova writes that coaching is an effective tool of adaptive personnel management and a means of achieving strategic competitive advantages of companies in the market. The authors studied the types of coaching, a set of socio-economic and psychological factors on which modern coaching technologies are based, and defined a set of professional competencies of coaches [2].

Wickstrøm et al. study the relationship between the propensity of small business managers to participate in training programs and changes in their strategic orientations. According to the authors, positive changes in strategic orientations occurred in managers with a low or medium level of propensity to participate in programs [3].

Atiase et al. study the impact of management training on the performance of managers in of SMEs in Ghana. The authors find that availability and content of training are statistically significant in explaining managerial performance, while training effectiveness and frequency are statistically insignificant [4].

M. Claeys et al. prove that improving the frame of reference of line managers, for example, by organizing meetings and/or trainings, can help them detect early signals of burnout and take action. This is the first step to prevent further development of burnout [5].

Collaboration between higher education and industry is a focus of academic programs, including those that target financial managers. However, the higher education-academia-industry triangle often lacks collaborative efforts to develop programs that address real-world problems.

P. Osipov et al. give recommendations on effective cooperation for training professional financial managers in university programs. The authors provide a number of recommendations for practical implementation of programs based on the experience of Kazan National Research Technological University (Russia) [6].

J.P. Thomas et al. studied the features of emotional intelligence of managers of Indian banks representing both public and private sectors. The authors conclude that emotional intelligence is a crucial factor in the activity of bank managers, and organizations should pay special attention to developing emotional intelligence of employees undergoing training programs [7].

Budiningsih et al. investigate the influence of the level of human capital and training on the professional behavior of Indonesian bank managers. The authors found that human capital and training contribute to the level of professionalism among managers [8].

P. Iodice et al. studied the effect of training self-regulation using neurobio-feedback on managers' intertemporal and risky decision making. The authors concluded that NBF training improves an individual's ability to self-regulate stress-related psychophysiological phenomena. Improving the ability to manage one's own stress response reduces instinctive behavior during a probabilistic choice task [9].

T. Yeardley assesses the relevance of trainings aimed at developing "soft skills" of managers, as opposed to "technical" or "hard skills", and determines whether there are prevailing managerial paradigms in the course content. The author believes his research informs HR departments of the inconsistencies in training new managers across providers, and highlights areas that new managers do not cover in courses. For training providers, it will be a reminder that training courses need to be constantly reviewed and revised to remain relevant, as the culture is rapidly changing from a society of personal interaction to a society of technology interaction. As a result, greater emphasis on communication, teamwork, and activities to develop intuition is required [10].

S. Muthumani and M. M. Kumar emphasize conflict management as one of the key abilities that significantly affects the performance of employees' daily duties. The authors' results showed that effective conflict management strategies affect the productivity of employees in the organization and suggested that conflict management training and retraining should be initiated to create a favorable atmosphere for employees [11].

Thus, the scientific problem of management training in the digital economy is the need to adapt educational programs and training methods to the rapidly changing requirements of the labor market. The digital economy also requires managers' knowledge of new technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, blockchain and others. With digitalization, the focus is shifting from traditional managerial skills to more modern skills such as analytical thinking, creativity, data skills and digital tools. The digital economy requires integration of knowledge from various fields such as IT, economics, sociology and psychology. Therefore, with rapidly changing technologies, managers must be prepared for continuous learning and self-development, and this requires continuous education and professional retraining systems.

RESEARCH RESULTS

All systems of the modern society are developing, and professional and personal qualities of the future head of the organization, including at the stage of higher education, are on the forefront. The most significant components of professionalism are the desire for cooperation and conflict resolution in any activity, and the ability to conduct a dialog, finding the most appropriate solution to the established differences. At the same time, an employee will be able

to resolve the contradictions they face only with conscious recognition of the prevailing values in modern society, while striving for innovation [12].

Against the background of the increasing degree of conflict in modern society in the conditions of digital transformation, the determination and ability of the future manager to apply knowledge, abilities and skills in professional activities to prevent and resolve various kinds of interpersonal conflicts, including conflicts originating in organizations, deserves increased attention. In the modern society, levels of conflict are heightened, so a manager needs to have the desire and aspiration to apply their knowledge, skills and abilities to anticipate and resolve interpersonal conflicts, including those arising in an organization with the subjects of relations. In this regard, now a significant means of overcoming the pressing problems of the organization is developing competence in terms of conflict resolution as an integral component of a manager's skills, especially in the framework of digital transformation.

In the modern practice of organizations, personnel needs to master the competence of conflict resolution, namely a set of conflict knowledge, technological skills and skills structured and adapted to the employee's profession.

We can testify that the set of methods and techniques of conflict resolution in today's workers is very limited and often implies authoritarian intervention, which leads to unreliable, short-term results without resolving the disagreement. Professional deformation and emotional burnout of the employee can also serve as a barrier to constructive interaction in conflict [13].

The management training programs aimed to develop conflict resolution skills are as follows:

MBA programs with a focus on conflict management. Various business schools offer courses within MBA programs that cover the topics of conflict management, negotiation, and mediation. These courses may include practical exercises, role-playing, and case studies.

Emotional Intelligence Courses. Programs that focus on emotional intelligence help managers better understand their emotions and the emotions of others, which is a key aspect of conflict resolution. Such courses may include trainings on self-awareness, empathy and stress management.

Mediation and negotiation trainings. Specialized trainings that teach managers mediation and negotiation techniques help develop the skills needed to resolve conflicts. Participants learn how to find compromises and reach agreements between conflicting parties.

Change Management Programs. Conflicts often arise in change environments. Programs that train managers in change management help them deal with the resistance and conflict that arise as organizations transform.

Cultural competency courses. With globalization, it is important to understand cultural differences that can lead to conflict. Programs that teach cultural competency help managers develop skills to work in multinational teams and resolve cross-cultural conflicts.

Simulations and role-playing. Some programs use simulations and role-playing to model conflict situations. Participants can practice their skills in a safe environment while receiving feedback from trainers and peers.

Online courses and webinars. Various online platforms offer conflict management courses that can be useful for managers who want to develop their skills in a flexible format.

These programs can be tailored to the specific needs of organizations and their employees, allowing for effective development of conflict management skills in different contexts.

Conflicts are perceived by the main subjects of interaction as a life phenomenon, which should not only be reckoned with but also actively influenced in order to prevent negative consequences and realize constructive opportunities. However, the nature of mutual claims which constitute the main part of socio-psychological tension in the society indicates that employees (including managers) of organizations do not possess sufficient knowledge and ideas about employee competence in terms of conflict resolution and, accordingly, effective practical ways of conflict management [14].

In most cases, conflicts arising in the work sphere are conditioned by the individual qualities of the participants, their subjective beliefs in relation to this or that problem situation, which seems to be of paramount importance for them and affects the individual space of personality. The employee is required to have the necessary competence either to prevent the conflict altogether or to apply effective strategies for resolving it [15].

Speaking about these necessary competencies, let us emphasize that in a broad sense, the ability to manage conflicts is a personal trait characterized by fundamental knowledge in a certain area, and having this trait determines whether the personality meets certain requirements.

The scientific opinion of conflict resolution competence is ambiguous, and the approaches to studying it are multidimensional, resulting in a wide range of its definitions. This concept defines such competence as the ability to effectuate measures to reduce destructive forms of conflict and to transform these in a socially beneficial direction.

Notably, the need for each employee to possess this competence, as well as its content and structure, is on top of the modern agenda. This competence includes knowledge of conflict resolution, technological skills and abilities, classified and adapted to the employee's profession.

Having analyzed scientific literary sources, we have come to the conclusion that to date, researches do not share a unanimous opinion on functional indicators of this competence. Some authors define the structure of employee competence in terms of conflict resolution through the following components:

Informational-value component implies awareness of the types, conditions, characteristics of the conflict, ways of their resolution, versatile view of the surrounding world, awareness of

the uniqueness of each personality, mastery of the basic methods of solving conflict situations and recognition of their importance for cooperation.

The integrative-activity component provides for the inevitability of establishing productive interaction with the subjects of conflict and the possibility of establishing such relationships, the ability to restructure external psychological attributes into personal empathy, tolerance, constructive behavior in conflict is fundamental in the procedure of self-knowledge.

The motivational component includes individual characteristics based on the rejection of oneself as a critic; the most important form of interaction is dialog, and the focus is on productive interaction.

Moreover, certain authors define the following structural components of the employee's competence in terms of conflict resolution:

- gnostic: awareness of the origin of the conflict, characteristic features of its evolution and development, communication and cooperation of conflicting parties in a situation of confrontation, their psycho-emotional state, etc.;
- projective: the ability to foresee the conflict, options for cooperation of the conflicting parties, the technologies of counteraction applied in the conflict, the course of the conflict, its effectiveness for the team and the conflicting parties;
- regulative: the ability to influence the confronting parties, to influence attitudes, assessments, motivation and goals of confrontation in conflict behavior, to influence public opinion towards the conflicting parties;
- communicative: the ability to establish effective communication between conflicting parties depending on their individual characteristics and psycho-emotional state;
- reflexive: the highest degree of self-knowledge culture, the ability of a group or organization to reflect, the ability to act in a certain way depending on the circumstances, goals and objectives of conflict coordination;
- normative: awareness of the normative-legal and moral side of behavior in conflict resolution, the collegial culture of leadership, the ability to rely on ethical and moral aspects in relations with conflicting parties.

Summarizing the position of scientists, it can be noted that the employee competence in terms of conflict resolution characterizes an integrative component of personality. This competence is determined by conflict knowledge, emotional self-control, culture of self-knowledge, and a wide range of components. Another interesting opinion characterizes the components of employee competence in terms of conflict resolution as follows:

Motivational-value: a set of value orientations united with altruistic moral and ethical ideals, a clear intention to build interaction on the basis of dialog, motivation to create trusting relationships in situations of interpersonal communication, motivation to overcome conflicts.

Intellectual and cognitive: maneuverability and productivity in considering the circumstances of interpersonal relations; intellectual activity as a feature of the personality, representing the integrity of cognitive motivated intentions, the ability to go beyond the designated boundaries, self-organization, contributing to the analysis of conflict situations.

Action-practical: communicative skills based on the ability to establish friendly relations with people, to understand their position, the ability to establish relations on humanistic principles, rational skills related to a person's ability to solve problems of effective conflict resolution.

Positional: determines the social orientation of a person, professional principles which allow to be aware of the socially significant role of conflict, resolution of professional confrontations through reaching an agreement between the participants of the conflict and constructing holistic relationships on this basis, the ability to control own emotional state, the degree of empathy [16].

In general, this model of management competence in terms of conflict resolution from the position provides for psychologically qualified actions and behavior in conflicts or situations of a destructive nature, rationalization of interaction with the opponent, protection of oneself from the danger of being drawn into an open conflict, and concentration of efforts for productive resolution of the conflict situation.

The problem of developing the competence of management personnel in terms of resolving conflicts between employees is becoming increasingly relevant in the context of optimizing interpersonal cooperation, which, in turn, is an integral component of the effectiveness of the process in the organization. Having conducted a comparative analysis of different approaches, we can say that it is necessary to specifically integrate individual personal qualities into components that will make up the structure of the manager's competence in terms of conflict resolution.

Thus, in modern conditions of an aggravated degree of conflict within society, the desire and will of the manager to apply knowledge, skills and abilities in work activities to anticipate and resolve various kinds of interpersonal conflicts, including conflicts arising in the organization with the subjects of relations, is of increased importance.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Research perspectives on conflict management training in the digital economy can focus on integrating knowledge from different fields such as psychology, sociology, political science and economics to better understand conflicts and conflict resolution techniques.

Using technology such as artificial intelligence and big data is helpful in analyzing conflict situations and developing effective management strategies. This may include conflict simulations and scenario-based learning.

Studying conflict in different cultural contexts will help develop more universal and adaptive culturally sensitive conflict management techniques.

Research can focus on developing training programs that help develop key skills such as emotional intelligence, negotiation, and mediation.

It is important to conduct research to evaluate the effectiveness of existing training programs to identify best practices and areas for improvement.

These areas can contribute to more effective training that can manage and facilitate conflict resolution in different spheres of life.

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